

MESOPP

Documentation of the definition of taxonomic/functional/energetic group in MESOPP models in relation to existing acoustic information

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Overview of MESOPP project

The underlying concept of MESOPP is the creation of a collaborative network and associated e-infrastructure (marine ecosystem information system) between European and Australian research teams/institutes sharing similar interests in: the Southern Ocean (SO) and Antarctica, its marine ecosystem functioning and the rapid changes occurring with the climate warming and the exploitation of marine resources.

In the past 30 years – facing global knowledge issues, lacking data and addressing huge modelling challenges – we observed the successful world organisation of meteorology. These past 15 years, Europe has kick started and achieved successful structuring of the operational oceanography fostered by the Copernicus initiative (<http://marine.copernicus.eu/>). Today, this structure is used and recognised worldwide and is integrated in GOOS (Global Ocean Observing System), IOOS (Integrated ocean observation system), SOOS (Southern Ocean Observing System), GODAE (the International Global Ocean Data Assimilation Experiment), and IMBER (Integrated Marine Biogeochemistry and Ecosystem Research).

The next major R&D strategic challenge is to connect the marine ecosystem community across the fields of meteorology, climate, oceanography and biology. This is a critical pre-requisite to overcoming (i) the domain's lack (or patchiness) of data, (ii) development of accurate high end to end models, (iii) global coverage and the need for exchange.

The objective of the MESOPP project is to meet this challenge and create links across the fields, pulling the marine ecosystem together. In particular, to:

1. Make an inventory of science challenges, stakes and existing policies and develop tools to federate and structure the community;
2. Start to organise the related marine ecosystem community between the EU and Australia through two implementation actions
3. Propose a R&D roadmap to support a large international cooperation on marine ecosystems based on an e-infrastructure, adding additional countries such as USA, New Zealand, Canada (in the Frame of the Galway statement), Brazil and all active countries already involved in large organisations such as IMBER, CCAMLR or IMOS.

MESOPP will focus on the enhancement of collaborations by eliminating various obstacles in establishing a common methodology and a connected network of databases of acoustic data for the estimation of micronekton biomass and validation of models. It will also contribute to a better predictive understanding of the SO based on furthering the knowledge base on key functional groups of micronekton and processes which determine ecosystem dynamics from physics to large oceanic predators.

This first project and associated implementation (science network and specification of an infrastructure) should constitute the nucleus of a larger international program of acoustic monitoring and micronekton modelling to be integrated in the general framework of ocean observation following a roadmap that will be prepared during the project.

1. Introduction

New marine ecosystem models are being developed that model multiple biophysical and socioecological components of the marine ecosystem, often coined end-to-end models (e.g. Fulton et al. 2011). Several different flavours of models exist, e.g. size-based models, food-webs models etc., but a common challenge is the number of complex links and number of model variables (Constable et al. 2017). Data is required to estimate the parameters in the model and assess their output, but data is scarce and expensive to obtain, especially for the mesopelagic (200 – 1,000 m) community (St. John et al. 2016).

Vertically discrete layers form during the daytime within the mesopelagic zone consistent of organism's (including crustaceans, small fish, squids and gelatinous organisms) typically smaller than 30 cm (Flynn & Kloser 2012, Proud et al. 2017). A proportion of the mesopelagic daytime community migrates vertically each night at dusk to feed at the surface under the cover of darkness, before returning to depth at around dawn (Brierley 2014, Bianchi & Mislan 2016). This regular and ubiquitous phenomenon is known as diel vertical migration (DVM), and facilitates the transfer of large quantities of carbon between the atmosphere and the deep ocean, commonly referred to as the biological carbon pump (BCP, Ducklow et al. 2001, Radchenko 2007, Passow & Carlson 2012).

Observations within the mesopelagic zone can be made using active acoustics (Medwin & Clay 1998, Simmonds & MacLennan 2005). Scientific echosounder's, such as the Simrad EK60/EK80 (Kongsberg Maritime, Norway), emit sound waves and detect backscatter from organisms in the water-column. Since we can determine sound speed in seawater very accurately (e.g. Mackenzie 1981), we can estimate organism depth by measuring the time difference between the emitted sound wave and received echo. Integrating catch/net-haul samples and/or acoustic scattering models with acoustic observations, provide a means to make inferences concerning species distribution (Anderson et al. 2005, Kloser et al. 2009, Proud et al. 2017), biomass (Hewitt et al. 2004, Irigoien et al. 2014) and behaviour (Lawson 2001, Cox et al. 2011). Typically, echosounders are hull-mounted and aimed vertically downwards. Their observational range varies with frequency, from 1000's m at 18 kHz to c. 200 m at 200 kHz. Echosounder's produce a pulse of soundwaves (of the order of ms in duration), commonly referred to as a ping, every few seconds, and are therefore an effective, rapid and non-invasive method of sampling mesopelagic communities.

Research vessels are typically equipped with multiple hull-mounted echosounders, with varying operating frequencies, usually between 18 and 200 kHz. Many deepsea fisheries vessels (ships of opportunity) are also equipped now with digital echosounders (e.g. FV Eros, FV Libas, FV Kings Bay) that can be calibrated to give quantitative data (e.g. (Ryan et al. 2009) Collected raw data are processed and archived in data centres e.g. MESOPP portal (www.mesopp.eu), NOAA National Centers For Environmental Information (<https://www.ngdc.noaa.gov/mgg/wcd/>) and IMOS (www.imos.au), following standardised metadata protocols set by the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) and are therefore readily available for large-scale analyses (e.g. Proud et al. 2017). The bulk of these data are collected at 38 kHz, making observations down to 1,000 m or more, meaning

that observations of the mesopelagic community are now made routinely throughout the ocean both during the day and night.

Although 38 kHz echosounder data provides adequate range to study the mesopelagic zone, the wavelength of the incident sound waves (c. 4 cm) limits observations of non-gas bearing organisms to those larger than c. 1 cm (unless aggregated at very high densities, e.g. Antarctic krill). Furthermore, at this frequency, fish and siphonophores (gas-bearing organisms) produce resonant backscatter (a sharp rise in echo energy by a factor of 10 or more at a specific size, depth and frequency, see Davison et al. 2015) at depth, which if not considered (e.g. Irigoien et al. 2014) could introduce considerable error in any derived estimates of biomass (Proud et al. 2018).

Recent work analysing 38 kHz acoustic data collected using hull-mounted echosounders, suggests that a large quantity of fish may reside in mesopelagic layers (11,000 to 15,000 MT, Irigoien et al. 2014) which could potentially provide food security for an increasing human population. However, the uncertainty around this estimate is extremely large (Davison et al. 2015), and a recent study using a simple food-web model suggests it is much lower (2,400 MT, Anderson et al. 2018), closer to an estimate made earlier, by Kawaguchi & Gjoseter (1980) of c. 1,000 MT, by analysis of ocean trawl data.

The reason for this uncertainty relates to our limited understanding and knowledge of mesopelagic scattering mechanisms. For instance, some siphonophores produce relatively strong echoes (Warren 2001) because they contain gas-filled bladders (like the swimbladder of fish) which are strong acoustic targets (density of gas is markedly different to the water and therefore produces a large acoustic impedance and hence a large scattering response). Siphonophores are gelatinous and are often destroyed in net hauls and so their abundance is very difficult to quantify – especially when they are at great depths i.e. in the mesopelagic zone. If we cannot attribute the correct proportion of mesopelagic backscatter to siphonophores (which is likely to be significant) then it is very difficult to make inferences concerning fish abundance and biomass (Davison et al. 2015).

Acoustics offers an opportunity to make observations of the mesopelagic zone and perhaps provide validation and parameter optimisation for the mesopelagic components of ecosystem models. To date, this has not been possible due to the complexity of ecosystem models and the lack of acoustic observations at adequate spatial and temporal scales. Acoustic observations at large scales are now possible (e.g. IMOS) but the interpretation of the data into biological units is complex due to the high diversity of species and different scattering mechanisms (e.g. resonance scattering) found within the mesopelagic zone.

1.1. This report

The challenge that this report addresses is how we can use acoustic data to provide validation of mesopelagic components within a range of widely used ecosystem models. To achieve this we propose that the model state is converted into acoustic signal and compared to acoustic observations i.e. using an acoustic observation model (see Section 4.2). However, a prerequisite to the development of the acoustic observation model, and the main objective of this report, is to demonstrate how acoustic observations, made at the currently widely

used 38 kHz frequency, relate to the mesopelagic components of ecosystem models. We do this by (i) reviewing the dominant scattering that drives acoustic observations for the mesopelagic community, and (ii) reviewing the segmentation of the mesopelagic community into ecosystem model groups in relation to the acoustics.

2. Mesopelagic Scattering

In this section we (i) review the dominant scattering mechanisms in the mesopelagic zone and determine what information is required to predict target strength of mesopelagic organisms using acoustic scattering models, (ii) review what information, concerning the acoustic properties of mesopelagic organisms that we already have, and (iii) discuss how acoustic observations may be scaled such that they could be compared to ecosystem model output.

2.1. Acoustic sensing in the mesopelagic zone

To make observations within the mesopelagic zone (200 – 1,000 m) using echosounders, an appropriate frequency must be used, such that the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is large enough to detect organisms down to 1,000 m. SNR increases with increasing wavelength (or decreasing frequency), e.g. at 200 kHz, the observable range is typically c. 200 m whereas at 18 kHz, it is likely to be > 2,000 m. A complication is that as frequency reduces and detection range improves, the minimum size of detected organisms increases, such that at 18 kHz, it is unlikely that fluid-filled zooplankton produce a substantial proportion of the received backscatter. There is however one exception. The gas-bladders of fish and siphonophores, are very strong acoustic targets, even when they are very small (< 1mm, see Fig. 1). This is because the strength of the returned echo/backscatter is related to the density difference between the seawater and the target's density, where the greater the difference, the larger the acoustic response (Simmonds & MacLennan 2005). In the case of gas-bearing organisms, the difference is very large and hence they produce strong echoes. In addition, gas-bladdered organisms can produce resonant backscatter at specific incident frequencies, depth and size ranges, which greatly increases their backscattering intensity (see Fig. 1) and can lead to great uncertainty in biomass estimates when not correctly accounted for (Davison et al. 2015).

Figure 1. Mesopelagic backscatter of a gas bladder (belonging to a fish or siphonophore), at 50 and 1,000 m, predicted using the resonance scattering model (see Appendix 6.1), and a fish body of length 4 cm and euphausiid 2 cm in length, both predicted using the DWBA acoustic scattering model. Size given for gas bladders is the equivalent spherical radius of the modelled prolate spheroid. Rayleigh and Geometric scattering regions are indicated along with resonant scattering.

Acoustic observations collected at 38 kHz provide a balance between an appropriate observable range for detection of mesopelagic organisms and minimum detectable size range. The target strength (TS, dB re 1m²) of an organism can be modelled by making simple approximations of target shape and assumptions regarding density and sound speed contrasts (Lavery et al. 2007, Scouling et al. 2015). Mesopelagic fauna is comprised of zooplankton, jellyfish, squid and fish over a range of different sizes. Using the appropriate acoustic scattering models, we predicted the TS over a range of frequencies for different mesopelagic organisms (Fig. 1). Only the gas bladder of siphonophores (pneumatophore) and

fish (swimbladder) was modelled (not the body tissue), since it is the gas bladder that produces > 95% of its TS (see Fig. 1 and Foote 1980).

In the first instance, mesopelagic organisms can be acoustically classified as either gas-bearing or non-gas-bearing organisms. Gas-bearing organisms are characteristically strong acoustic targets and can produce resonant backscatter (Fig. 1). Backscatter from their flesh/tissue is typically significantly weaker than their gas bladders (Fig. 1). Gas bladder TS was predicted here using a resonance scattering model (Scouling et al. 2015), assuming that the shape of the gas-bladder could be approximated by a prolate spheroid (see Appendix 6.1). The TS of gas-bearing organisms is also likely to change substantially with depth in accordance with Boyles Law, i.e. as a fish/siphonophore migrates vertically towards the surface, pressure decreases, and the volume of the gas-bladder increases. Conversely, non-gas-bearing organisms are typically weak backscatters (Stanton et al. 1996, Lavery et al. 2007), represented here by a euphausiid modelled using the distorted-wave born approximation (DWBA, Chu et al. 1993). They do not produce resonant backscatter and, assuming that orientation remains constant, their TS does not change with depth.

At 38 kHz, gas-bearing and non-gas-bearing organisms can be classified into 3 different scattering types related to size (a) and angular wavenumber ($k, 2\pi/\lambda$): 1.) Rayleigh, $ka \ll 1$, 2.) Intermediate, $ka \approx 1$, and 3.) Geometric, $ka > 1$ (Simmonds & MacLennan 2005). The TS of a Rayleigh target is dependent upon its volume and increases linearly with increasing frequency (Fig. 1); orientation of the organism has little to no consequence on TS. Conversely, the TS of a geometric target is dependent upon shape and orientation, not volume. In between these regions, it is difficult to predict TS and gas-bearing organisms within this range can produce resonance (Fig. 1). Using this information, 6 scattering groups were defined, ranked by their likely contributions to mesopelagic backscatter (see Fig. 1) and described by their scattering properties and model input parameters (Table 1). Gas-bearing organisms (scattering groups 1 to 3) will likely dominate the acoustic response in the mesopelagic zone (Fig. 1), and their orientation, depth and size ranges will drive the magnitude of that response.

Table 1. Scattering groups, defined by their scattering properties and scattering model input parameters. Groups are ranked by their likely contributions to mesopelagic backscatter, from 1 (high proportion) to 6 (low proportion). An example is given of an organism that would typically belong to each group.

Scattering group	Example fauna	Scattering properties				Scattering model Inputs		
		Gas-bearing	Rayleigh	Intermediate	Geometric	size	depth	orientation
1	Myctophid/Siphonophore (small gas bladder)							
2	Myctophid/Siphonophore (large gas bladder)							
3	Juvenile Myctophid							

4	Squid/Jellyfish							
5	Antarctic krill							
6	Copepod							

2.2. Existing acoustic information

Gas-bearing organisms can be split into two groups, gas-bladdered fish and gas-bladdered siphonophores. To predict the mean TS of a population of fish or siphonophores it is important to know what proportion have gas-filled bladders; without this information, the uncertainty is very large (Proud et al. 2018). Given we know that proportion, we review here what information is already available concerning the size, depth and orientation of the two groups (see Table 1).

The majority of mesopelagic fish are myctophids; there are c. 250 species worldwide and they are found everywhere in the ocean (www.fishbase.org). Size at maturity of these fish ranges from 2cm to c. 30cm but typically is c. 8 cm (www.fishbase.org) and their daytime depth ranges throughout the mesopelagic zone, but typically is c. 500 m (Proud et al. 2017).

To predict mesopelagic fish TS, we need to know the size of their gas-bladder, not the size of their body. The gas bladder volume of marine fish is typically c. 5% of body volume for marine fish and c. 7% for freshwater fish (Marshall 1971) and increases with size (allometric growth) and condition (length-width ratio). Given that we know the size of the fish, we can estimate its gas bladder size based on this relationship. This, however, is not always the case, the swimbladder of myctophids is typically much smaller (0.01-2.63% of body volume, Yasuma et al. 2010) and its growth with age varies between and within species (Yasuma & Yamamura 2010, Scouling et al. 2015). Moreover, in some instances, the gas-bladder volume reduces as the fish grows older; this is a consequence of investiture of lipids within the swimbladder, as an alternative buoyancy strategy. Not much is known regarding the orientation of myctophids at depth, but there is some evidence that they are immobile, unless preyed upon, conserving energy in a torpid state (Catul et al. 2011). But in the absence of empirical evidence, we assume a broad normal distribution of orientations (see Table 2).

There is little information regarding the size and depth distribution of gas-bearing siphonophores (physonects and cystonects). Their gas bladders range from < 0.15mm (Lavery et al. 2007) to > 2mm (Barham 1963) and their body size range from cm's to 10's m. The paucity of information concerning siphonophores is perhaps the largest source of uncertainty when making estimates of biomass using acoustic data in the mesopelagic zone (Proud et al. 2018).

The existing acoustic information is summarised in Table 2. In the absence of any other information, these values could be used in conjunction with acoustic scattering models to predict abundance of fish/siphonophores in mesopelagic layers. The broad range of the parameter values listed here will likely lead to very large uncertainty in these predictions. Additional information, provided by ecosystem models for example, may reduce this

uncertainty and enable us to compare predictions of mesopelagic backscatter to acoustic observations (see Section 4.2).

Table 2. Existing acoustic information required for predicting the target strength of gas-bearing organisms (mesopelagic fish and siphonophores).

	Size range (mm)	Depth range (m)	Orientation	Gas-bladder volume (% of body volume)	Length-width ratio	Proportion with gas-bladders
Fish	20-300 ^{R1}	200-1000	N(0,30)	0.01-2.63 ^{R3}	4-12 ^{R4}	0-1
Siphonophores (gas-bladder)	0.01-40 ^{R2}	200-1000	N(0,30)	NA	NA	0-1

R1: www.fishbase.org

R2: (Barham 1963, Robison et al. 1998, Lavery et al. 2007)

R3: (Yasuma & Yamamura 2010)

R4: (Flynn et al. 2012)

2.3. Upscaling acoustic observations

Echosounders operating at 38 kHz typically sample the mesopelagic zone every c. 2 s (sound speed in water c. 1500 ms⁻¹) with a vertical sampling interval of c. 80 cm (pulse length c. 1 ms). This resolution of sampling is much higher than the scale typically output by regional-scale ecosystem models (days to months over large areas of the ocean, see Constable et al. 2017). To scale these outputs to the same spatial and temporal resolution, acoustic observations can be integrated over depth ranges within the mesopelagic zone for a given area. A common metric used in acoustics is the volume backscattering strength (S_v , dB re 1m⁻¹), which is the mean backscattering intensity over 1m³. To scale this measure up to a representative mean over the entire mesopelagic zone, we calculate the area backscattering coefficient (s_a , m²m⁻²), by integrating the linear values of S_v (s_v) between 200 and 1,000 m:

$$s_a = \int_{200}^{1000} s_v dz, \quad (1)$$

where z is depth. Values of s_a can be calculated over any depth range, area, and time-period output by an ecosystem model, given that acoustic observations are available, and the area is defined in m².

3. The mesopelagic components of ecosystem models

In this section we review how the mesopelagic components of the ecosystem models used in MESOPP are grouped and at what scales (depth, space and time) the models produce their output.

3.1. Model groups

Five ecosystem models are considered in MESOPP: Atlantis, Ecopath (high latitude and Kerguelen Plateau), SEAPOYDM, MIZER and WOMBAT. These models were documented and compared in the MESOPP report “Documentation of the models, approaches for their standardization and protocols to be used for model inter-comparison in MESOPP” and ranged in complexity from a simple model with two functional groups, WOMBAT (phytoplankton and zooplankton) to ATLANTIS, with 43 functional groups, ranging from bacteria to whales (Constable et al. 2017).

3.1.1. Mesopelagic components of ecosystem models

In each of the ecosystem models used in MESOPP, the mesopelagic component is represented differently. Whilst fish are generally separated from zooplankton and other scatterers (e.g. squid and jelly fish), siphonophores are mixed in with a variety of other zooplankton species (Table 3).

Table 3. Biological representation of mesopelagic components of ecosystem models used in MESOPP which can be observed using acoustics (extracted from Constable et al. (2017), Table 1). Grey shaded cells indicate processes or components that are not represented. Green shading highlights groups that contain dominant scatterers (mesopelagic fish and siphonophores). An * indicates an age or size structured representation for that group.

Size	Atlantis	Ecopath (high latitude)	Ecopath (Kerguelen)	SEAPOYDM	MIZER	WOMBAT
200µm-2cm	Meso-zooplankton	Meso-zooplankton	Zooplankton, herbivores	Meso-zooplankton	Initially as resource spectrum, explicit representation under development	Zooplankton
	Macro-zooplankton	Copepods	Zooplankton, omnivores			
> 2cm		Macro-zooplankton				
2-20cm	Salps	Salps		6 micronekton functional groups	Small-medium nectonic squids*	
	Krill*	Antarctic krill	Euphausiacea			
		Other krill				
	Cephalopods	Squid and octopus	Cephalopods small			
	Fish pelagic*		Small pelagic fishes			
	Fish mesopelagic*	Myctophids			17 taxa of mesopelagic sand bathypelagics*	

Size	Atlantis	Ecopath (high latitude)	Ecopath (Kerguelen)	SEAPODYM	MIZER	WOMBAT
20cm-1m	Fish Pelagic*		Large pelagic fishes	Target species (large pelagic fish)		
	Fish Mesopelagic*	Antarctic silverfish				
		Demersal fish	Large benthic fishes			
			Other benthic fishes			
		Bathypelagic fish				
	Cephalopods	Squid and octopus	Cephalopods large		Ommastrephiids* Onychoteuthiids*	
	Toothfish*	Antarctic toothfish	Patagonian toothfish, juveniles		Patagonian toothfish* (northern model); Antarctic toothfish* (southern model)	
Patagonian toothfish, adults						
Icefish*			Icefish*			

3.1.2. Resolution of ecosystem models

The spatial and temporal resolution of ecosystem model output varies considerably between models (Table 2) and is typically at a much lower resolution of time, depth and area than acoustic observations (see Section 2.3). Three models resolve depth (Atlantis, SEAPODYM and WOMBAT) to varying degrees (Table 4) and two resolve the day to night change due to DVM (Atlantis and SEAPODYM, see Constable et al., 2017).

Table 4. The resolution and scale of ecosystem model output.

Scale	Atlantis	Ecopath (high latitude)	Ecopath (Kerguelen)	SEAPODYM	MIZER	WOMBAT
Space	Multiple irregular polygons	Single region	Single region	Various (0.08°- 2°)	2 boxes	Various (0.1-1°)
Depth	10 depth layers	NA	NA	6 depth layers based on euphotic depth	NA	2 depth layers
Time	User defined (e.g. 12 hours, monthly, annually)	Monthly	Monthly	7 days	Various (weekly, monthly, annual)	Various (weekly, monthly, annual)

3.2. Converting ecosystem model output to acoustic signal

Ecosystem models typically output abundance/biomass for each model group and provide various other information such as depth range, size range, condition, etc. To convert these values to s_a (area backscattering coefficient) values (see Section 2.3) for comparing to acoustic observations, we use the same acoustic scattering models described in Section 2.1, substituting these with information from Section 2.2 where required. For example, given an abundance per unit area (n) of mesopelagic fish, the mean TS in linear units, the backscattering cross-section, is given by

$$\overline{\sigma_{bs}} = 10^{\frac{\overline{TS}}{10}}, \quad (2)$$

and is predicted using the appropriate scattering model (see Appendix 6.1) and multiplied by n , to determine the predicted area-backscattering coefficient, \hat{s}_a , given by,

$$\hat{s}_a = n\overline{\sigma_{bs}}. \quad (3)$$

This can then be compared to the observed s_a and used to validate/parameterise the mesopelagic component of ecosystem models (see Section 4.2).

4. Discussion and Summary

In this report, we have reviewed the dominant sources of 38 kHz mesopelagic backscatter (Section 2.1) and identified what information is required to predict acoustic signal (Section 2.2). We have also reviewed how the mesopelagic community is represented by ecosystem models and at what scale (Section 3.1). Using existing biological information concerning the acoustical properties of mesopelagic organisms (e.g. fish and zooplankton, see Section 2.2), output from the mesopelagic components of ecosystem models (Section 3.1) could be converted to values of \hat{s}_a (Section 3.2). These predictions of acoustic mesopelagic backscatter could then be compared with upscaled acoustic observations (Section 2.3) to provide ecosystem model validation/parameter optimisation and facilitate the development of an acoustic observation model (see Section 4.2 and Proud et al., 2018). An acoustic observation model would allow us to compare ecosystem model output with acoustic observations but requires a better understanding of acoustic backscatter selectivity at 38 kHz.

4.1. Acoustic selectivity

The current and widely available acoustic backscatter data, suitable for uptake into an observation model, have been collected using echosounders operating at a frequency of 38 kHz. These observations of the mesopelagic zone during the daytime are likely (based on the Target Strength models) to be dominated by backscatter from gas-bladdered fish and siphonophores (Fig. 1 and Proud et al. 2018). Target strength models require information regarding organism size, depth, and orientation to make predictions of backscatter (see Section 2 and Appendix 6.1). We currently have little understanding regarding the size and depth distributions of these organisms and in particular, data concerning siphonophores (but developments are under way using acoustic and optical probes, Kloser et al. 2016). Acoustic observations are made at high spatial and temporal resolutions (meters and seconds). These observations can be upscaled by integration over the mesopelagic zone and averaged over an area and time-period of interest to match the scale of the output of various ecosystem models e.g. IMOS (www.imos.au) upscales collated echosounder data to a resolution of 1 km transect distance by 10 m depth bin sizes.

4.2. Acoustic Observation model

The mesopelagic community can be represented by a variety of different taxonomic/functional groupings and at various spatial and temporal scales in ecosystem models (Constable et al. 2017), which typically fall into broad size ranges and groupings of either zooplankton or fish (Table 3). These groupings make sense in terms of functional groups (Constable et al. 2017), but may not be grouped in terms of similar acoustic scattering properties, which makes the conversion from model biomass to acoustic signal more uncertain. If the model outputs the key acoustic information, the conversion can be made with less error, otherwise the conversion will be highly uncertain. The uncertainty in such a conversion, will determine the validity of comparing those predictions to acoustic observations. The parameters that are needed to convert the mesopelagic component into acoustics are rarely explicit in the ecosystem models, and the uncertainty in the conversion is

often high. To predict mesopelagic backscatter from abundance/biomass data output from ecosystem models, we need to know what proportion of each model group contains gas-bladdered fish or siphonophores, and their size and depth (Section 2.2). There are also other parameters that can reduce uncertainties in the conversion. Knowledge of the condition of the species, for example, would reduce uncertainty in gas-bladder size and weight of fish. Identification of eco-regions with relatively homogeneous species communities to which the same acoustic observation model can be applied would also greatly facilitate the development and validation of ecosystem models.

4.3. Way forward

To reduce uncertainty in the conversion of ecosystem model output into acoustic signal, we recommend the following i.) Increased observations of the mesopelagic community at depth using acoustics coupled with optical probes (Kloser et al. 2016, Demer et al. 2017) to improve existing acoustic information, ii.) Ecosystem model design that considers what information is required by acoustic scattering models to predict acoustic observations e.g. depth and proportion of gas-bladdered organisms, and iii.) Ecosystem model design that segments the zooplankton community into gas-bearing and non-gas-bearing organisms. The Atlantis ecosystem model provides depth, size and condition information for each mesopelagic grouping. The model is also capable of separating out gas-bladdered and non-gas bladdered fish species (pers. comms. Beth Fulton), which makes it an ideal test-candidate for application of the acoustic observation model.

5. References

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6. Appendix 1:

6.1. Resonance scattering model

The backscattering cross-section, σ_{bs} , can be predicted using the resonance model described by Scouling et al. (2015):

$$\sigma_{bs} = \frac{a_{esr}^2 (\rho_w / \rho_f)^2}{(\omega_0^2 / \omega^2 - 1)^2 + \delta^2(\omega, a, b, \xi; \Omega)} D(k, a, \theta, \sigma), \quad (A1)$$

where ω_0 is the angular resonant frequency, taken from love (1978) and is found by solving

$$(\omega_0 a_{esr})^2 = C_e(a, b) \frac{3\gamma_a P_z}{\rho_f} + \frac{2s}{\rho_f a_{esr} (3\gamma_a - 1)}, \quad (A2)$$

a_{esr} is the equivalent spherical radius given by

$$a_{esr} = (ab^2)^{1/3}, \quad (A3)$$

where a and b are the semi-major and semi-minor axes of the prolate spheroid respectively and are related by the b -scaling parameter, β , given by

$$a = \frac{b}{\beta}, \quad (A4)$$

γ_a is the specific heat ratio for gas (1.4), δ is a damping factor, s is the surface tension, ω is the angular incident frequency, ρ_f is flesh density, $N(\theta, \sigma)$, k is the wave number, D is the directivity function (Stanton 1988) average of a normal distribution of orientation angles (θ), C_e is a spheroidal elongation factor based on the work of Strasberg (1953) and Weston (1967), P_z is pressure at depth ($P_z = z/10 + 1$, where z is depth in meters), Ω is a set of damping constants and ξ is the dynamic viscosity. See Table 1 in Proud et al. (2018) for values of parameters/constants used to calculate the TS of fish and siphonophores.